

Pl@ntNet-API

Case Studies

Demonstrating Cos4Cloud success stories
and best practice examples

Description

This case study is an output from the [Cos4Cloud project](#) which demonstrates evidence-based knowledge of project approaches and their impact. It is part of a collection in the [Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#) and shared as part of the legacy and lessons learned from the project. These include a range of stories and experiences collated from activity generated throughout the lifetime of the project

Case study title

Use cases of Pl@ntNet-API in an app for farmers and to identify plant-pollinator interactions

Pl@ntNet API website © Inria and Pl@ntNet-API

Service Coordinator

Case study contributing partners

What is the case study about?

This case study demonstrates the potential of the Cos4Cloud service [Pl@ntNet-API](#) in two different use cases to query the Pl@ntNet identification engine allowing the integration of an automatic plant identification feature into an app and workflow, respectively, without having to manage the plant identification feature itself.

Pl@ntNet-API is an Application Programming Interface (API) allowing users to query the Pl@ntNet identification engine. This service is available to developers, researchers and other citizen science observatories interested in plant biodiversity.

Pl@ntNet-API enables other citizen observatories and third-party applications developed by industrial, academic or associative stakeholders to integrate automatic plant identification features very easily into their apps. This service is regularly updated and enriched with new flora images, because it is connected to the Pl@ntNet database. This means that the visual recognition is constantly improving.

This service has been developed by [Inria](#) in the Cos4Cloud project framework and is available on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Marketplace, [here](#).

The two use cases described are based on interviews with Pl@ntNet and Pl@ntNet-API users Tom August ([Fabó Cartas, 2022a](#)) and Nadja Pernet ([Fabó Cartas 2022b](#))

CHALLENGE: WHAT DID THIS SEEK TO DO / SOLVE?

Use case 1: Integration of Pl@ntNet-API into an app for farmers

The [UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology \(UKCEH\)](#) is one of the national foci for citizen science in the UK. They are involved in over 80 recording schemes and societies such as the UK butterfly monitoring scheme or the ladybird survey, among many others. They validate, verify, analyse data and work on species distribution modelling and trends analyses using occupancy models. The UKCEH also collaborates with citizen science or citizen-led organisations and helps the recording community to analyse their data, publish atlases and other online resources, providing information essential for research, policy and conservation.

The UKCEH also works on monitoring the agricultural environment: This usually involves experiments asking farmers to farm in a particular way and then expert surveyors monitoring the impact of different farming strategies by doing botanical surveys and other measurements. In this context, the use of Pl@ntNet-API was seen as a way to give farmers more agency and the ability to undertake some of these botanical surveys with the help of an artificial intelligence (AI) for plant identification.

The UKCEH built the app [E-Surveyor](#), which was launched in June 2022. This is a tool that allows farmers to monitor the habitats on their farms or land using the Pl@ntNet-API to identify plants from many different species. By querying the Pl@ntNet identification engine through the Pl@ntNet-API the app quickly identifies or recognises the plant species that users (farmers or others) have uploaded. Through this, farmers are able to see what species – from the ones they have sown – have grown successfully, e.g. wildflowers to support pollinators.

The UKCEH has data on plant-insect interactions, as well as information on which plants host natural enemies of crop pests. So, after a farmer conducts a survey with the help of the AI, the app provides information about which pollinators their habitat is supporting and other beneficial insects that can help to control the pests on their crops and evaluates the quality of the habitat ([UKCEH 2022](#)).

Photo: E-Surveyor interface on an iPhone
(Source: <https://www.ceh.ac.uk/e-surveyor>) © UKCEH (UKCEH 2022).

This will increase awareness about natural enemies and decrease the use of pesticides. For instance, if a farmer has lots of plants that are providing habitat for ladybirds, which eat aphids, then the farmer will not need to use as much pesticide to control aphids and can time their use of pesticide based on how many ladybirds they have.

Use case 2: Use of Pl@ntNet-API to identify plant-pollinator interactions

Trained biologist and postdoc researcher Nadja Pernat is interested in iEcology. iEcology uses big data from online platforms, not only citizen science platforms but also other webpages, social media, everything that contains images, text, etc. to find out if the data out there can contribute to the global biodiversity collection of data and if ecological research can be done with it. She was interested in plant-pollinator interactions caught on images provided by citizens to citizen science platforms such as [iNaturalist](#).

The research question she wanted to use the Pl@ntNet-API to investigate was: how to identify the plants that an insect is sitting on from a picture and integrate the automatic species recognition into an automatic workflow.

The chosen species selected to learn more about plant-pollinator interactions was a species of wasp not native to Europe called *Isodontia mexicana* (the Mexican grass-carrying wasp). Many iNaturalist pictures of this wasp were available but not much literature about them. Nadja found out about the *plantnet* R package, which can be used to communicate with the Pl@ntNet-API, via the R statistical programming language that Tom August from UKCEH (see [use case 1](#)) had developed. Using this she developed an automatic workflow.

Photo: iNaturalist observation of the Mexican grass-carrying wasp (*Isodontia mexicana*) visiting a plant in its non-native range, in Luxembourg. Credit: CC0, observation available [here](#).

This demonstrates an example of the use of Pl@ntNet-API through R; without having to access the Pl@ntNet-API directly. Nadja retrieved all the picture URLs of *Isodontia mexicana* from iNaturalist with a specific R package (several packages are available to communicate with the iNaturalist API) and fed them into the Pl@ntNet-API with the help of the *plantnet* R package. Also, for every image, Pl@ntNet-API returned a list of candidate species of plants potentially shown in the picture together with the wasp as well as their scores (likelihood of the image being species 'x' or 'y').

BENEFITS AND OR OUTCOMES

Use case 1: Integration of Pl@ntNet-API into an app for farmers

The main benefit that Pl@ntNet-API provides for the [UKCEH app E-Surveyor](#), is breaking down taxonomic barriers. The integration of automatic plant identification allows farmers, land managers and other app users to monitor and better understand their land or farm and the interaction between the habitat and insect species, without needing to be trained ecologists.

Pl@ntNet returns a list of species and the likelihood of the image being species 'x' or 'y' after a user uploads a plant photo. Pl@ntNet also includes a tool to find the most similar photo (species) from the Pl@ntNet database compared to an uploaded observation. This not only helps identify species easily but also offers the possibility to falsify suggestions by the AI and improves quality control. These functionalities are common to both Pl@ntNet and Pl@ntNet-API.

Lastly, Pl@ntNet-API and the Pl@ntNet database it queries are regularly updated and enriched with new flora images. This means that the visual recognition is constantly improving. To put it simply, Pl@ntNet-API offers the integration of automatic plant identification into an app while not being dependent on having to manage the plant identification feature itself.

Use case 2: Use of Pl@ntNet-API to identify plant-pollinator interactions

In this study, Nadja wanted to obtain information about which plants *Isodontia mexicana* was visiting to (1) assess the accuracy of Pl@ntNet identifications, (2) create a list of plant species, (3) identify possible flower colour preferences and (4) recognise possible other ecological interactions captured in the images. The preprint of the study is available [here](#) on a preprint server. The results surmised that the workflow developed and the performance of the Pl@ntNet algorithm were quite useful to generate research questions for a first exploration of an introduced species or a species about which not much is known.

Similar to use case 1, the Pl@ntNet-API allowed automatic plant identification so botanist skills were not indispensable to study plant-pollinator interactions. The list of species and the likelihood of the image being species 'x' or 'y' that Pl@ntNet returns after a user uploads a plant photo served Nadja to assess the accuracy of Pl@ntNet identifications – the assistance of expert botanists was enlisted for the study.

This Cos4Cloud case study demonstrates two examples of the use of Pl@ntNet-API in real scenarios. Pl@ntNet-API is a service developed by Inria in the Cos4Cloud framework.

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Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

This case study demonstrates two use cases of the Cos4Cloud Pl@ntNet-API service in real scenarios. Developed by INRIA, the Pl@ntNet-API is one of the of the co-designed services developed as part of the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **Title: Use cases of Pl@ntNet-API in an app for farmers and to identify plant-pollinator interactions.** Main author: Claudia Fabó Cartas. Contributors: Jaume Piera, Karen Soacha, Sonia Liñán (ICM-CSIC); Ángela Justamante, CREAM. This Case Study is part of the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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